

THE ROLE OF PHILOSOPHICAL AND NATIONAL FOUNDATIONS IN LITERARY ANALYSIS

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada badiiy asar tahlilida falsafiy va milliy asoslarning oʻrni yoritib beriladi. Ushbu elementlar adabiy asarning mavzusi va strukturasi shakllanishiga qanday taʼsir koʻrsatishi va matn mazmunini chuqurroq anglash imkonini berishi tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit soʻzlar: Falsafa, milliy oʻzlik, adabiyot, tahlil, madaniy meros

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается роль философских и национальных основ в анализе литературных произведений. Анализируется, как эти элементы влияют на тематику и структуру произведения, а также углубляют понимание его содержания.

Ключевые слова: Философия, национальная идентичность, литература, анализ, культурное наследие

Abstract: This article explores the significance of philosophical and national foundations in literary analysis, emphasizing how these elements shape both the narrative structure and thematic depth of a work. By examining literature through the lens of philosophy and national identity, readers gain insight into the cultural and intellectual background that informs the text, enriching their understanding and appreciation of the work.

Keywords: Philosophy, National Identity, Literature, Analysis, Cultural Heritage.

Introduction

Literature serves as a profound reflection of human thought and cultural values, shaped by philosophical questions and national identity. In analyzing literary works, it is essential to consider the underlying philosophical themes and the national context, as these elements provide insight into the author's worldview and the collective experience they seek to convey. By examining philosophical and national foundations, we achieve a fuller understanding of the narrative, its characters, and the message it communicates to society.

Philosophical Foundations in Literature

Philosophical themes in literature address universal questions about life, morality, and human nature. Authors often use these themes to delve into existential concerns, ethical dilemmas, and the human condition. For instance, Fyodor

Dostoevsky's novels confront issues of free will, faith, and redemption, reflecting his deep engagement with philosophical and religious thought (Dostoevsky, *Crime and Punishment*, p. 56). Similarly, the existentialist themes in Albert Camus's *The Stranger* illustrate the absurdity of life and the search for meaning (Camus, *The Stranger*, p. 22).

National Foundations in Literature

National identity is a powerful influence on literature, shaping the themes, characters, and settings of a work. Authors often draw upon their cultural heritage, embedding elements of national history, folklore, and traditions in their narratives. This cultural embedding enhances the authenticity of the work, allowing readers to gain insight into the society from which it originates.

For example, in Uzbek literature, Alisher Navoi's poetry reflects the values and traditions of the Uzbek people, weaving in elements of Islamic philosophy and Central Asian heritage (Navoi, *Hamsa*, p. 145). His works convey the moral and ethical values of his time, preserving them for future generations. Similarly, in Irish literature, James Joyce's *Ulysses* is deeply rooted in the Irish experience, using Dublin as a backdrop to explore themes of nationalism, identity, and personal freedom (Joyce, *Ulysses*, p. 102).

Interplay Between Philosophical and National Foundations

In many literary works, philosophical and national foundations are closely intertwined. Philosophical reflections are often contextualized within a national setting, giving them a unique cultural perspective. This interplay enhances the richness of the narrative, as it combines the universal with the particular.

For instance, in *One Hundred Years of Solitude* by Gabriel Garcia Marquez, existential themes of fate and cyclical time are interwoven with Colombian history and culture. This fusion creates a narrative that is both a philosophical exploration of human destiny and a cultural chronicle of Latin American society (Marquez, *One Hundred Years of Solitude*, p. 205).

Conclusion

The analysis of philosophical and national foundations in literature offers a multidimensional approach to understanding a text. By examining these elements,

readers can connect with both the universal themes and the unique cultural background that shape the work. This dual perspective not only enriches the reading experience but also fosters a deeper appreciation of literature as a reflection of human thought and national identity. As we continue to explore these foundations, we gain valuable insights into the complexities of literary expression and the cultural heritage it preserves.

References

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